

A STUDY ON ACADEMIC STRESS AND PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO PALAKKAD DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

College students today face a myriad of challenges that can significantly impact their psychological well-being. High levels of academic stress, stemming from factors such as heavy course loads, financial constraints, and social pressures, have been shown to contribute to a range of mental health concerns, including anxiety, depression, and even suicidal thoughts. This study aims to investigate the relationship between academic stress and psychological well-being among college students in the Palakkad district of Kerala, India. The study includes both primary and secondary data. The findings of this research will provide valuable insights into the nature and extent of this issue, as well as identify potential interventions to support student mental health and overall well-being.

Keywords: *Academic stress, psychological well-being, college students etc..*

INTRODUCTION

The curriculum serves as a quantifiable plan and structure that equips teachers, students, school administrators, and community members with the necessary resources to provide a high-quality education. By outlining the learning objectives, standards, and core competencies that students must exhibit before progressing to the subsequent level, the curriculum acts as a guiding framework. Teachers are instrumental in crafting, applying, evaluating, and adapting the curriculum. An evidence-driven curriculum functions as a roadmap to facilitate teachers and students in achieving academic success. However, college students often experience significant levels of stress, anxiety, and depression, which can negatively impact their physical and mental well-being as well as academic performance (Austria-Cruz, 2019).

Psychological well-being has become a prominent focus in psychology, as it is a crucial aspect of individual fulfilment. According to the fourteenth Dalai Lama, the fundamental purpose of life is to attain happiness. From the moment we are born, every human being strives for happiness and seeks to avoid suffering. Neither social conditioning, education, nor ideology can alter this innate desire. At the core of our being, we simply yearn for contentment. While the universe with its countless galaxies, stars, and planets may hold deeper meanings, we humans living on this earth must create a life of happiness for ourselves. Therefore, it is crucial to discover the means to achieve the highest degree of happiness.

Academic stress can substantially influence a student's psychological well-being, leading to various alterations in their social interactions and behaviours. These changes can manifest with differing degrees of subtlety and intensity across individuals. Some common social and behavioural adjustments associated with academic stress include:

- Withdrawal from social activities
- Decreased enthusiasm for interpersonal interactions
- Irritability and emotional outbursts
- Modifications in communication patterns
- Changes in appetite, such as loss of appetite or overeating
- Sleep disruptions
- Anxiety in social settings
- Avoidance of academic-related discussions
- Substance use
- Reduced empathy.

A multitude of factors contribute to elevating academic stress among university students. Increased academic demands, such as heavy course loads, frequent examinations, and challenging assignments, can significantly strain students' mental and physical capacities (Rothkopf & Schworm, 2021)(Richardson et al., 2023). Additionally, the pressure to excel academically and meet the expectations of parents, peers, and institutions can exacerbate stress levels.(Duffy et al., 2020)

LITERATURE REVIEW

BUSARI (2012) found that stress was leading to depression among secondary school students and is linked with an effect on academic achievement. Introduction to preventive measures, teaching life skills, and other therapeutic techniques should be taken into serious consideration.

KHAN AND KAUSAR (2013) concluded that stress negatively impacts academic performance though no significant difference was found as per gender. The difference was evident between junior and senior students. Stress, for sure, affects the ability to study efficiently and manage time. Studying regularly is important, this helps reduce academic pressure and helps them fulfill their goals.

GHAHFAROKHI F. (2015). A review of the effectiveness of stress management skills training on academic vitality and psychological well-being of college students. Carrying out the appropriate psychological interventions to improve vitality and mental well-being is critical. The study was carried out to review the effectiveness of stress management training on the academic life and mental well-being of the students of Shahed University.

SHARMA (2016) focused on various methods to curb stress. Working out regularly is one of the best ways to relax your body and mind. One can also use the idea of various time management techniques and get engaged in leisure activities which can benefit students. Also, it was suggested that colleges should adopt measures to reduce stress. Change in the way of communication with the students may lead to a lack of stress.

DIMITROV (2017) studied that the students should give more importance to their welfare they should concentrate more on areas such as food, exercise, work, recreation, etc. The study also pointed out that the education system should contribute more with academic qualifications and thus, help in the development of the students. English is the only available option that can act as a hindrance for students from rural backgrounds.

REDDY. (2018) concluded that academic stress exists course-wise. Some of the remedies recommended in the study include feedback, yoga, life skill training, mindfulness, meditation, and psychotherapy have been found to deal with stress. A person needs to identify the reason for stress to deal with it. Curbing stress among college students is important not only for the individual but for the institution as well.

HJ RAMLI N. H., ALAVI M., MEHRINEZHAD S. A., AHMADI A. (2018). Academic stress and self-regulation among university students in Malaysia. Academic stress is the most common emotional or mental state that students experience during their studies. Stress is a result of a wide range of issues, including test and exam burdens, a demanding course, a different educational system, and thinking about the future upon graduation.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The transition to college life is a critical phase in a student's academic journey, characterized by various challenges and adjustments. One of the most prevalent issues faced by college students is academic stress, which can have a profound impact on their overall well-being and psychological behaviors. The proposed study aims to investigate the relationship between academic stress and psychological well-being among college students.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To investigate the association between academic stress and psychological well-being among students.
2. To analyze the disparities in academic stress between male and female college students.
3. To examine the differences in psychological well-being between male and female college students.

METHODOLOGY

Sample Size

The study was conducted by taking a sample of 63 college students from various arts and science colleges in Palakkad District. The data collected through online survey.

Sampling Techniques

The study adopted convenience sampling technique for selecting respondents.

Data Collection & Analysis

The study includes both primary and secondary data. The study adopts a well-structured questionnaire and data that are randomly collected from respondents from the Palakkad district. The secondary data were collected from journals, research studies and websites. The simple percentage analysis has been used to analyse the data.

The study also uses Descriptive and Analytical research design. Samples were collected from 63 respondents through structured questionnaires.

RESULTS & INTERPRETATION

TABLE 1: SHOWING THE GENDER CLASSIFICATION

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Male	30	47.6
Female	33	52.4
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

The above table shows the gender-wise classification in which male consists of 48% of the total population and 52% of the population is female.

TABLE 2: SHOWING THE AGE CLASSIFICATION

Option	Frequency	Percentage
18 to 20 years	38	60.3
20 to 25 years	25	39.7
Above 25	0	0
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, 60% are between 18 to 20 years old and 40% are between 20 to 25 years old.

TABLE 3: SHOWING THE EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION

Option	Frequency	Percentage
UG	63	100
PG	0	0
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, 100% of students belong to the graduate Category.

TABLE 4: SHOWING THE TYPE OF INSTITUTION

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Govt	21	33.3
Govt. aided	26	41.3
Self-financing	16	25.4
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, 33.3% of students are studying in Government colleges, 41.3 students are from government-aided colleges, and the rest 25.4% of students are from self-financing colleges.

TABLE 5: SHOWING THE COURSES

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Arts	16	25.4
Science	18	28.6
Commerce	29	46
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, 25.4% of students are from Arts, 28.6 students from science and most of the students (46%) are from Commerce.

TABLE 6: SHOWING THE STUDENTS ACADEMIC STRESS

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	51	81
No	12	19
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, 81% of students are facing academic stress and 19% of students are not facing it.

TABLE 7: SHOWING THE IMPACT OF STRESS ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	13	20.6
Agree	36	57.1
Neutral	9	14.3
Disagree	5	8
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, 57.1% of students agree that stress has a significant impact on their academic performance.

TABLE 8: SHOWING THE STRESS BASED ON GENDER CLASSIFICATION

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	29	46
No	34	54
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, 54% of respondents agree that there is no difference in academic stress based on gender.

TABLE 9: SHOWING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Excellent	6	9.5
Good	28	44.4
Fair	20	31.7
Poor	9	14.4
Very poor	0	0
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, the overall psychological well-being among students is good by 44.4%.

TABLE 10: SHOWING THE POOR ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE DUE TO ACADEMIC OVERLOAD

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	24	38.1
Agree	22	35
Neutral	13	20.6
Disagree	4	6.3
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, 38.1% of students strongly agree that academic overload leads to academic performance.

TABLE 11: SHOWING THE REMEDIAL MEASURE UNIVERSITY TAKEN

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	25	40.3
No	37	59.7
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

The above table states that universities do not take any remedial measures to reduce academic overload.

TABLE 12: SHOWING THE ACADEMIC STRESS DUE TO THE CURRICULUM SYSTEM OF UNIVERSITY

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	14	22.2
Agree	21	33.3
Neutral	20	31.7
Disagree	8	12.8
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, 33.3% of students agree that the curriculum system of the university causes academic stress.

TABLE 13: SHOWING THE TEACHER'S ROLE IN REDUCING ACADEMIC STRESS

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	46	73
No	17	27
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

The above table shows that teachers have a significant role in reducing academic stress.

TABLE 14: SHOWING THE STUDENT'S PRESSURE DUE TO UNEXPECTED EXAMS

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	24	38.1
Agree	28	44.5
Neutral	4	6.3
Disagree	4	6.3
Strongly disagree	3	4.8
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

The above table shows that unexpected exams lead to high pressure among students.

TABLE 15: SHOWING THE DELAY IN THE PUBLICATION OF RESULTS

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	28	44.4
Agree	25	39.7
Neutral	6	9.5
Disagree	3	4.8
Strongly disagree	1	1.6
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, 44.4% of students strongly agree that delay in the publication of results makes further studies more difficult

TABLE 16: SHOWING THE ABILITY TO COMPLETE ASSIGNMENTS AND PROJECTS

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Excellent	4	6.3
Good	34	54
Average	19	30.2
Below average	4	6.3
Poor	2	3.2
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, 54% of students are good at completing assignments and projects before the deadline.

TABLE 17: SHOWING THE AVAILABILITY OF SUFFICIENT RESOURCES FOR STUDIES

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	45	71.4
No	18	28.6
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, 71% of students agree that they get sufficient resources for their studies and the rest agree that they do not get any sufficient resources.

TABLE18: SHOWING THE SATISFACTION WITH THE AVAILABLE RESOURCES

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	39	62.9
No	23	37.1
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, 63% of students are satisfied with the available resources and 37% of students are not satisfied with the available resources.

TABLE 19: SHOWING THE CAREER UNCERTAINTY AMONG STUDENTS

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	23	36.5
Agree	25	39.7
Neutral	10	15.9
Disagree	5	7.9
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

The above table shows that career uncertainty is a major problem among students.

TABLE 20: SHOWING THE OPPORTUNITIES IN INTERNSHIPS AND PLACEMENTS

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	8	12.7
Agree	14	22.2
Neutral	15	23.8
Disagree	17	27
Strongly disagree	9	14.3
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, 27% of students disagree that there are no opportunities for internships and placements. 22.2% of students agree that there are more opportunities in internships and placements and 23.8% of students are neutral.

TABLE 21: SHOWING THE TECHNOLOGY DISTRACTION AMONG STUDENTS

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	21	33.3
Agree	20	31.7
Neutral	19	30.2
Disagree	3	4.8
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, 33.3% of students strongly agree and 31.7% of students agree that technology distraction is one of the major problems of poor performance.

TABLE 22: SHOWING THE PEER PRESSURE AMONG STUDENTS

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	26	41.9
No	37	58.1
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, 58% of students agree that they have peer pressure and 42% of students do not agree with it.

TABLE 23: SHOWING THE ENGAGEMENT IN EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES AND STRESS MANAGEMENT

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	16	25.4
Agree	29	46
Neutral	14	22.2
Disagree	4	6.4
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, 46% of students agree that engaging in extracurricular activities helps in stress management among college students.

TABLE 24: SHOWING THE INVOLVEMENT OF FRIENDS AND FAMILY IN MANAGING ACADEMIC STRESS

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Always	13	20.6
Usually,	23	36.5
Sometimes	16	25.4
Rarely	7	11.1
Never	4	6.4
Total	63	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation

From the above table, 36.5% of respondents accept that their friends and family are supportive of managing academic stress.

TABLE 25: SHOWING THE PERSONAL METHODS TO RELIEVE STRESS

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Yoga	12	19
Exercise	23	36.5
Social media	36	57.19
Sports	19	30.2
Eating	23	36.5
Sleeping	31	49.2
Doing adventure	19	30.2
Others	16	25.4

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, social media (57.19) and sleeping (49.2) are the most used personal methods to relieve stress.

TABLE 26: SHOWING THE METHODS UNIVERSITY CAN ADOPT TO RELIEVE STRESS AMONG STUDENTS

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Internships	30	47.6
Skill enhancement	32	50.8
Training programs	31	49.2
Restructure the syllabus	28	44.4
Semester breaks	34	54
Orientation classes	20	31.7
Motivational and personality development classes	18	28.6
Peer teaching	11	17.5
Counselling	17	27

Value added courses	16	25.4
Policy changes	14	22.2
Gender sensitization programs	10	15.9

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, semester breaks (54%), internships (47.6%), skill enhancement (50.8%), and training programs (49.2%) are the most suggested methods university can adopt to relieve stress among students.

TABLE 28: SHOWING THE ABILITY TO HANDLE STRESS WHILE EXPERIENCING IT

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Excellent	4	6.3
Good	22	34.9
Fair	20	31.7
Poor	11	17.5
Very poor	6	9.6
Total	63	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, 34.9% of students are good at handling academic stress and 9.5% of students are very poor at handling stress while experiencing it.

FINDINGS

- The findings indicate that most of the participants were female undergraduate students aged 18-20
- Most of the respondents are primarily from government-aided colleges and the Commerce stream.
- A significant proportion reported experiencing academic stress, with most students believing that such stress varies based on gender.
- While most participants reported having good psychological well-being
- Many agreed that academic overload led to poor performance.
- Additionally, most students felt that universities did not take sufficient remedial measures to address this burden.
- Opinions were mixed regarding the university's curriculum system as a source of academic stress, but teachers were seen as playing a crucial role in mitigating such stress.
- Unexpected exams and delayed result publication were identified as significant contributors to student stress.
- Most participants demonstrated good time management skills in completing assignments and projects
- The majority had access to sufficient study resources, which they generally expressed satisfaction with.
- However, career uncertainty and mixed opinions on internship and placement opportunities remained concerns for many respondents.

- Technology distraction was found to negatively impact student performance, while extracurricular activities and socialization were effective stress-relieving methods.
- Participants also felt that the curriculum should be improved to develop essential life skills, and social media was a common outlet for stress relief.

DISCUSSIONS

College represents a transformative period for students, marked by significant academic and social demands. Navigating this transitional phase can be particularly challenging, as students must contend with increased responsibilities, financial pressures, and the need to establish new social connections. These stressors can profoundly impact students' psychological well-being, potentially undermining their academic performance and overall quality of life. The present study aims to investigate the relationship between academic stress and psychological well-being among college students in Palakkad District, Kerala, India. Drawing on existing research, this paper explores the prevalence of stress-related issues, the factors contributing to academic stress, and the strategies employed by students to maintain their psychological well-being. Existing literature underscores the pervasive nature of academic stress experienced by university students. Factors such as parental expectations, peer competition, and the demands of a rigorous academic curriculum can contribute to heightened levels of stress, which may, in turn, lead to adverse mental health outcomes, including anxiety, depression, and even suicidal ideation. Hence, appropriate measures should be taken to reduce stress and thereby enhancing the wellbeing of students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- To encourage student attendance, classes should be made more engaging through the implementation of effective strategies that promote interaction, facilitate the acquisition of academic skills, and foster inner benefits related to the syllabus. prepare our students for real-world employment opportunities, equipping them with relevant job-related skills.
- A "learning by teaching" system should be introduced, whereby students are encouraged to deliver lectures using their abilities and skills to delve deeper into the subject matter. This approach would help minimize gaps in understanding among students about the topics covered.
- Institutions should allocate mandatory time for physical activities, enabling students to engage in extracurricular physical pursuits despite tight schedules.
- Immediate counselling sessions, accompanied by warm-up exercises such as yoga and meditation, should be provided at the school and college levels to help students maintain a fresh and calm mindset, free from stress or anger.
- A modern curriculum should be adopted to appropriately
- Institutions should foster a friendly campus atmosphere to encourage student comfort, thereby reducing stress levels significantly.
- The traditional mode of examination evaluation needs revamping, with new assessment methods implemented to value each student's unique abilities.
- By replacing conventional teaching methodologies with innovative approaches that stimulate active engagement, academic pressures can be alleviated and the latent talents of students can be uncovered.
- Properly scheduling assigned tasks to be completed during regular college hours can help mitigate the issues of sleep deprivation and over-commitment that many students face today.

CONCLUSION

The study titled "A Study on Academic Stress and Psychological Well-Being Among College Students with Special Reference to Colleges in Palakkad District" aimed to assess the academic stress and psychological well-being of college students, as well as identify the factors and challenges contributing to their academic stress. The key sources of stress for the students include inadequate support, a rigid evaluation system that limits their ability to experiment and excel, and various personal and social factors. The lack of clear career guidance and the unavailability of competent counsellors lead to uncertain career goals, leaving students feeling directionless and insecure about their future employment prospects. Additionally, the increasing pressure from academics, extracurricular activities, and assignments, coupled with parental expectations to outperform their peers and maintain a high social status, have exacerbated the stress levels among the students. Academic stress has a significant detrimental impact on students, leading to an increased prevalence of psychological, physical, and mental health issues. Severe consequences such as fatigue, insomnia, and anxiety are commonly observed among students facing high levels of academic stress. Anxiety, in particular, can negatively affect students' social, emotional, and academic well-being.

This narrative review highlights the central focus of the study, which examines the impact of academic stress on the psychological well-being of college students in Palakkad district. The study emphasizes the importance of addressing stress among students and underscores the crucial role of the curriculum, teachers, and preventive measures in improving students' mental health. Furthermore, the study reviews various research findings on stress management and proposes strategies such as regular exercise, time management, and engaging in leisure activities to alleviate stress among students.

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